

Scalar Magnetic Waves and Qi

And other related topics...

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Preface

This article is a bit ahead of its time, but shall serve as the hypothetical arm of research to be conducted using equipment from [Professor K. Meyl](#) regarding his alleged discovery of Scalar Magnetic Waves. Based upon his and other experimenters around the world, scalar electric waves do exist, and his equipment shows clearly the ability to send data using modulated resonant scalar frequencies as opposed to the normal types of radio signals by utilizing a flat disc shaped Tesla copper coil as transmitter and receiver, and standard spherical antenna made famous by tesla's power stations. Through this setup, Meyl has demonstrated wireless power transfer with notable features such as heightened efficiency at low voltage, and receptivity at receiver despite shielding.

The Electromagnetic Force, or “The Force”

To understand however, magnetic scalar waves, and the discussion to follow, one must understand something about electro-magnetic force.

This Universe is, as I have shown, 3 dimensionally simulated because of the consciousness which unites the two differently oriented planes of the physical brane-space and the potential or Void space, what seekers and religions call the Spirit World. The Mind or Heisenberg observer unites these two by changing waves of potential data into particle data that remains “fixed” but of course is actually constantly in flux.

The consequence of this for the EM force, when talking about the 3 Dimensional space is what is known as the “right hand rule”:

Simple RHR showing basic directions of EM force

This shows the direction of flux in a magnetic field; showing direction of current will be perpendicular to the force.

In reverse this means also that the magnetic force can be supposed as a result of electrical flow, for instance as electrons move in a circular direction. This will become important later on, so remember it. It is the basis for all AC (alternating current) three phase power generation (ie, your home's electricity at the power plant).

Now, the scalar magnetic waves are therefore the result, naturally, of the scalar electrical force, and nothing more. The lack of detection in science is nothing more than the inability to create extremely fine gaussian magnetic force sensors for extremely small scales. But we know in Qi gong that even a complete beginner can create a magnetic repulsion force between their hands and/or another person's, and even generate action potentials in the nerves detected by sensations of heat and tingling in the peripheral nerves. However, all attempts to find this using standard EM force detection, such as voltmeters, amp-meters, etc.. have failed. However, research has conclusively shown that meditation does create EM currents inside the brain, and has been even mapped using fMRI and other techniques.

So this is our dilemma. To show why these scalar waves exist, what their effect should be, combine with the theory by using the macro-empirical research of thousands of years of meditation that have demonstrated conclusively that there are strange effects and powers of the human mind, including telekenesis, electrical transference, and even from the Huang Di Nei Jing and New Testament, miraculous healing powers which seem divine (tong-shen-ming in Chinese, Holy Spirit in gnosticism). there is now, thanks to Professor Meyl, a scientific, rational basis for these effects, and practical applications which I will briefly mention at the end.

In order to continue, it is highly recommended to review all of the available interview and demonstration videos, listed here in order of most important first, to least, according to technical demonstration down to theoretical supposition.

1. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9tplRbd-fso>
2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9AFY3QlTrRg> (min 35+)
3. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tKTkpC-DHZ8>
4. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e8ZcTCI325Q>
5. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F7SR4vF_pug
6. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bfcLjllsLnQ>

The first three videos are sufficient, however, the last three provide other theoretical semi-metaphysical framework that will enable us to explain some special effects, such as Astrological phenomenon, Geomancy, etc... which will be briefly mentioned after the discussion of Magnetic Scalar Waves and Qi (as an addendum to the main hypothesis).

Now the basic thing that the individual must understand, in order to understand the miraculous or practical effects of Qi (according to the Electric Universe model Tesla promoted*) is that the B (magnetic) field runs perpendicular up (using RHR) to the counter-clockwise flow of electrons.

What Professor K. Meyl noticed is that within DNA and organic chemistry you have these Benzene hexagonal rings, which have been long ago demonstrated to shared electrons in a continuous flow, not restraining them to the individual atoms.

This circular movement creates a small particle charge differential, resulting in a small but nevertheless magnetic field. Most organic chemists and physicists will agree there. (see image)

[A Benzene Ring producing a B field](#)

*Tesla, and many others of his time were highly skeptical of strange new theories. I am not discounting the research of quantum or relativistic physics, or even String Theory. I am noting here, however, the idea of a single Unified Field that is merely scaled for distance would be lauded not only in Taoism, but in non-linear mathematics which sees the Universe from a fractal (recursive) perspective, rather than linear (such as one-dimensional time as we perceive it).

Above - same
Left - top view

What Prof. Meyl also noticed, as have others, is that these rings are part of the Base pairs in DNA:

Note the dots represent changing bonds, not rings.

What you have to understand now, is that there is another effect whereby power transformation occurs through utilizing wrapped coils to transfer the magnetic field through a closed system. A simple transformer:

Theoretically, without losses, if the right and left coils are equal then there is a 1:1 transfer without closed circuit connection of the left and right circuits. More important than power level, because we don't care about nor can calculate losses, we care that there IS a transfer of the magnetic field along a changing, 3-dimensional medium. This is important, because DNA is not straight or square, but coiled in a double helix.

Flat for easy reference, but not true to the shape; this shows the benzene rings of base pairs:

Simple double helix

Notice even the sides of the strand are pentagonal rings. However, again not representing the true shape

Now we see more accurately the close-packed spacing of the ring structures. Even though there are bound to be losses in the B field due to the rings not lining up, the overall effect is a subtle (weaker than radio wave power) transfer of the B Field, propagated by successive benzene (and sugar) rings.

The moving B field propagates in a circular sinusoidal wave. In a linear wave, or ordinary EM wave, we see the following shape:

[The famous Faraday Wave](#)

The Resulting understanding of the EM spectrum is:

This shows not simply wavelength of light, but also Planck wavelength based on size of the body or object

Now, however, this B field is changing direction constantly, so the overall B field is producing an Electrical force in a **vortex pattern**.

HOWEVER, that isn't the end. Each DNA strand is further coiled such that there is an overall E field that runs through the center of these coils, generally perpendicular to the B field propagated along the coil, producing another larger B field.

Electron Scanning Micrograph of real* DNA - not a model

*Please note the molecules seem ball like because their electrons are repulsing the electrons, but they are not round, but mostly empty space.

As is shown here this is repeated and repeated until there is a 30 nm Solenoid, in other words a coil, and these are in turn wrapped up and creates the same vortex shaped B field that we see at the benzene ring level, propagating along the DNA coils throughout the chromosome, such that there is a B field like so, and an overall resulting electrical force, in other words, electrical wireless signal (a transmitter).

The solenoids create a B field, and this creates a twisting electrical current which in turn runs along the inside of the coils resulting in an overall turning E field, which creates a B field inside the overall coil. This results in a B field emerging from the chromosome.

Basic idea

RED= B (magnetic flux)
GREEN=E field (current)

Each ring acts as a Motor
there are two coils, so two
overall coiling B fields

The overall effect is
shown at right

E Field propagates
along coil

E fields of
coiled DNA
"arms"

B Field

histones create oscillation, turns negate
each other overall, resulting in A/C like
sinusoidal wave

If there is a wave, there is a frequency, if a frequency
then there is a signal and antenna, meaning that there
is a transmission of data at a frequency modulated by the shape

If there is a wave, created by the current passing through the histones, as shown above, then there is a **modulated frequency**.

Now, DNA is not pretty and perfect as shown above. In fact it is often twisted, irregular, and mangled. However, in most traditional meditation, there is a concept that **Qi only arrives through “alignment.”**

Consider standard magnetic fields in lodestones (iron filings). In iron, if it is cooled in the absence of a magnetic field, it will create random shaped crystals. However, in a magnetic field, such as the Earth's, it will produce a regular pattern and make the iron magnetic.

Similarly, I am postulating that there are methods of DNA/chromosomal level control which enable a person to activate or change the shape of their DNA from a majority being misaligned, “crumpled” or irregular to being aligned, at least in such a majority as to create an overall B field, such that the individual(s) can sense this field.

Such changes would likely be the effect of any one or all of the following:

- Changes in the cellular structure by microtubules in response to electrochemical stimuli coming from endorphins, neurotransmitters, or hormones (such as epinephrine).
- The existence of a heretofore undiscovered (but much researched) organ-like tissue call Connective Tissue (The San Jiao in Chinese Medicine), which has an autonomic nerve response to the same stimuli
- The movement of action potentials surrounding tissues propagating more or less in linear fashion in any region, creating an alignment of nearby cellular nuclei and other structures, such as mitochondria, which may facilitate energetic data transfer locally.
- Other unknown currents and EM field transmissions in local systems as yet undiscovered.

It would be important to remember that the EM field is particularly weak at long distances, however, like gravity not inexistent; see Galactic Clusters. So although the chromosomes are inside the nucleus, and the nerves outside the muscle and organ tissues, the “channels” in Chinese medicine are the overall flow of energy along these tissues, meaning that there is indeed an effect or force-field felt simultaneously by the nerves and the cell tissues.

It may be hard to imagine the nerve has a strong enough B Field surrounding it to induce chromosomal alignment, but perhaps it is the overall area all having this B field due to multiple nerves firing which leads to chromosomal alignment.

If this alignment occurs, then certainly it is possible that the chromosomes start projecting their own B fields as shown above, and this would affect the nerve-conduction. Indeed, the entire swirling vortex of EM fields would be a **constantly vibrating machine**, and could explain the effects Qi practitioners of Qigong, Taichi, or Yoga feel as they activate “chakras” or areas such as palms or soles of the feet.

The effects are **real**, we merely have yet to identify non-metaphysical models that explain these phenomena, which are decidedly **not** placebo, nor psychosomatic. The methods of meditation, alchemy, and trance have been studied by cultures as various as mystical Jewish, gnostics, shamans, yogis, zen, taoists, zoroastrians, vikings, pagans, native Americans, aborigines, polynesians, etc... and so these effects as empirically well tested and established. More and more, greco-roman-anglo westerners have become intrigued by these cultures and seek them out, spending billions annually to study their sciences.

SO... what is missing is an understanding of how they work from a materialist-reductionist standpoint.

Modulated Frequencies and Epigenetics; Quantum data-shifting.

One of the interesting phenomenon that are being documented, such as here:

<http://shambhalatimes.org/2011/10/20/before-and-after-portraits-from-dathun/>

and in reverse here:

<http://www.upworthy.com/mesmerizing-photographs-of-soldiers-faces-before-and-after-a-war>

Is the effect of Quantum data-shifting. As anyone can easily see, the features and even volume and density of the faces can change in a relatively short period of time due to sustained efforts in either the positive or negative, or even healing from trauma.

Now, although we know that cells repair and change, and can degrade under stress (see Telomerase), there is no reason to expect that they can change as rapidly as that, or even as I have demonstrated using the Mirror Flushing technique, within 5 minutes, changing even teeth color and eye reflectivity (giving me an apparent "twinkle").

More curious is how individuals with depression have remarked that being given acupuncture the room can appear to suddenly brighten up, as if the eyes are filled with light. And indeed, brain scans show these effects in the change from dull brains (low activity or suppressed activity), to bright ones:

(note - could be achieved by **any** method that treats depression)

When acupuncture is performed, many people feel: whole or partial body buzzing, tingling, heat, roving sensations, nerve twitchings, muscle fasciculations, spasmodic or relaxing sensations, and psychosomatic or emotional release (often emotions not stored in the brain but in muscular nerve plexuses or organ tissues, such as the uterus).

These feelings result in outer **and** inner changes, that have been well documented through tongue, pulse, eye color, facial complexion, and an effect known as microperfusion in the skin. (see PubMed)

Such changes are remarkable, but easily dismissed through electro-chemical or mechanical explanations. However, when you combine the psychic changes along with the changes in their facial structure, weight, volume, or density, especially in such a short period of time, there is no doubt that there is something that seems less like a rolling billiard ball, and more like a **modulation** of frequency.

Modulation is the carrying of low frequency data in high frequency wave carriers. AM or FM radio is the classic example, but there are others.

What do we mean by long wave or low frequency? Anything below 200 kHz is long wave. The human ear hears at maximum 25-30 kHz, most people far less. Brain waves and the Earth's B field is in the 10-15 Hz range.

Planck's law states that a frequency (inversely related to wavelength), is related to the mass of the body or object. So even as a person sits still, or the Earth goes along its disc around the sun, the fact is that it is oscillating along a long wave, calculated by using Planck's equation. However, these lengths are typically invariably long wave or low frequency. Sound familiar?

Now considering Dr. Meyl's calculations, which show that the DNA signal is in the 22 MHz range we can see that there is a frequency modulating relationship between the total overall body's wavelength and the DNA average (mean) frequency. Through this one can find out what "radio station" a person is tuned into, if one can only find their mean HF (microwave) DNA frequency. Not an easy task.

However, two new factors also come into play. First there is the fact that each individual has differing amount of irregularities in the DNA such as coiling, errors in DNA, illnesses, and junk DNA. Secondly, epigenetics holds that although most genes (and their shapes) are typically set since early adulthood, actually they can still change due to environmental stressors (such as emotions, hypothermia, starvation, and you guess it: meditation). Now we are seeing why the results in the before and after pictures show such drastic changes.

As people alter their behaviors and stressors, they alter the telomerase and epigenes which shape their DNA (and age it). Then as this changes, their frequency itself can change. If they also change their macro-level low frequencies (such as weight, or brain waves), they then completely alter the "vibe" or signal they transmit to others. 2,500 years ago, the Nei Yeh (internal cultivation, or Original Tao) called this the "wordless pronouncement"* It essentially was a signal to other people and the Universe at large as to how a person should be treated, how they would treat others, their rewards and punishments. The first reward and punishment in life is one's health or illness. Now we see the rational explanation (as opposed to the metaphysical, or superstitious, or anthropological explanation) of how Tong Shen Ming (divine penetrating illumination) or something such as shamanistic "touchless" healing, or in modern times "reiki" worked.

*Verse 18

- 1 When there is a mind that is unimpaired within you,
- 2 It cannot be hidden.
- 3 It will be known in your countenance,
- 4 And seen in your skin color.
- 5 If with this good flow of vital energy you encounter others,
- 6 They will be kinder to you than your own brethren.
- 7 But if with a bad flow of vital energy you encounter others,
- 8 They will harm you with their weapons.
- 9 [This is because] the wordless pronouncement
- 10 Is more rapid than the drumming of thunder.

- 11 The perceptible form of the mind's vital energy
- 12 Is brighter than the sun and moon,
- 13 And more apparent than the concern of parents.
- 14 Rewards are not sufficient to encourage the good;
- 15 Punishments are not sufficient to discourage the bad.
- 16 Yet once this flow of vital energy is achieved,
- 17 All under the heavens will submit.
- 18 And once the mind is made stable,
- 19 All under the heavens will listen.

transl. Harold D. Roth, *The Original Tao*, Nei Yeh, Inner Cultivation [\[Available on Amazon\]](#)

Tesla Coils in the body? The Scalar Magnetic Hypothesis of Qi

Aside from preposterous theories of Qi, including ones as insulting as supposing Indian Ayurveda, Christian Gnosticism, and Chinese Medicine all invented a placebo effect to explain the normal healing powers of the body, there are two very equally plausible models to explain Qi. Professor Meyl, may have even linked them both together.

1. Qi is scalar magnetic waves which are generated by aligned chromosomal combined magnetic vortex flux, transmitted by highly charged individuals modulating their frequencies actively (using nerves or some electro-chemical means as opposed to the soul or spirit) and thereby changing their Resonant Frequencies. The implications of this being that it explains such effects in humans as telekinesis, psychic data exchange, prediction of harm in others, sensation of pain despite not being nearby or able to see the harm inflicted on others, sensing danger or tragedy, possibly pyrokinesis (by hands), electrical control in some humans that has not been easily explained otherwise (such as John Chang and Slavisa Pajkic).
2. Qi might merely be a heretofore undiscovered or immeasurable (due to human interaction) particle, the wave being what we sense somehow, and the particle being what our mind senses or observes through unexplored abilities in the brain, perhaps some kind of result of the brain being an organic quantum computer. Examples could be Dark Matter, Dark Energy, Higgs-Boson, or neutrinos.
3. The neutrino actually is the supposition of Professor Meyl, but no way to prove this at this time.

However, although we cannot rule out any of the above, there is anthropological and cultural support for the first, rather than the vague notions of animism such as the “spirit world” being the equivalent to the invisible Universe (Dark Matter and Dark Energy).

This evidence harkens back to Professor Meyl’s re-production of Tesla’s coils in flat copper coiled-discs.

Here we see the [correct spins for the chakra spirals for male and female](#); the idea being that the chakras are “coils” of “channels”. Most Jing-luo (channels) run generally laterally or longitudinally, however, the chakras are historically noted as coils. Although they are more toruses, from the front they appear as coils.

The Ren and Du Mai (channels) circulate over a long time, producing very minor E fields as the magnetic flux rises (shakti) These sensations are not just palpable to the individual but to others and machines as well*

* <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21138386>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/10841380>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/9142560>

<http://www.slideshare.net/anken/kundalini-psychosis-or-transcendence>
<http://biologyofkundalini.com/article.php?story=BiologicalRelationtoZero-Point>

Below - Diagrams of the other macro-circulating “extra-ordinary” meridian, the Dai-girdle Mai, which also powers the Sacral and Root Chakras, and they in turn power its movement. The price people pay for sitting excessively are a long list of genitourinary issues, including cancers, cysts, endometriosis, prostate (various), and hemorrhoids or other anal issues, all related to chakra degradation.

The Internal Flow of the Kidney Qi

Unsubstantiated "electro-graph"

Yoga Pranayama Awakens Kundalini Powers

Note - sacral spiral and hand toroids

The I Ching is a time-tested, well respected source text on quantum synchronicity through the Polar Universe
 In other words, the world's first scientific paper on charges, dipoles, and the Electro-magnetic and
 wave-particle duality of the Universe.

CHAKRA ASSESSMENT - INITIAL VISIT

Major Modifier: **EMOTIONS**
 Minor Modifier: **WILL**

Other Comments:

Client name: **D**

Date of first visit: **02.mars.05**

Presenting Complaint: **Depression**

Unsubstantiated Diagram showing chakra vortices

Internal workings of chakra vortices, includes the 3 auric levels of Wei Qi

1st: 1cm->½ in above skin

2nd: 3-6in above skin

3rd: 1-3 feet above skin

the larger the Wei qi field, the stronger the chakra vortices, or what in EE we would say the more Work they are performing, creating a larger B Field output. It is important to note that this is an amorphous B-field with only now a general direction of polarity along the “Microcosmic Orbit” but also a field which spins according to the hemisphere of the Earth, along the axis of the Taiji Pole running from the Perineum (RN1) to the skull vertex (Du20)

This spin does create a minor electrical charge, and hence people who are aligned have a certain “shine” and “gravity” or “magnetic attraction” to them known as Te (De) - inner power. Also, they stand more erect, seem thinner, brighter, sharper, and have more sexual gravitas, which translates as has been shown to charm and salesmanship. What they say even seems to have more “force”. All of these vernacular indicate a physics-based alteration. I have observed that they even seem denser and more fit, stronger than those out of alignment. A fact that is the basis for the Egoscue Method and Pilates, as well as Yoga.

Human Chakra System = **Tesla Coil**

Tesla Coil Function

Power Source, HV Transformer, Spark Gap, HV Capacitor, Primary Coil, Top Load

Tesla Waves
Human Telepathy

Humans in resonance LOVE

The Sun, Magnetosphere Reconnection, Van Allen Belt, Earth Field Line, Human

HRONOYA.ORG
The Body of CHRIST
NOOSPHERE

PLASMOID, HV Capacitor, Spark Gap, Earth Magnetosphere

Above and below > more spirals in the culture of Yoga and Ayurveda (a medicine dubbed the Science of Life)

EM spectrum relating to 7 chakras - 7 chakras, 7 colors we can see. Not a coincidence.

Speaking from the Quantum Body perspective, 8 physical laws of the Universe, 8 trigrams, 8 overall chakras including the one hovering over the head, 8 senses*, and the octaves of sound, as well as the 8 divisions of the EM spectrum: ULF, Radio, Microwave, IR, Color, UV, XRay, Gamma/UHF.

It may be that other Universes are set up differently, but it is clear that our bodies have evolved to enable us to sense “in the middle” and survive “in the mild”.

*sight, smell, hearing, balance, proprioception, taste, temperature, pressure

內經圖

學明之結明打無首
 此法善釋太國體
 即門運軸極國諸
 不也中精季而子
 明不氣種強悟太

Top - the Taijitu classically included in Tesla coil
 Above - The precise origins of chakra vortices from Chinese Medical perspective (as opposed to Yoga/Ayurveda) This shows dual anthropological evidence which cannot be dismissed as "placebo" or other ethnocentric polemic statements from Greco-Roman based (aka White) "Science"

The Classical Nei Jing Tu, shows a clear spiral in the

“Mysterious Pass” which is typically noted to be halfway between solar plexus and heart chakras.

A diagram showing the Reflexology of Kundalini (spinal vortex) and the palmar - from Ayurveda

The Seven Main Chakra

Reflexology Chart Showing Major and Minor Chakra

Above and Below: More Vortices and at Right, Field lines (Jing mai)

More research on Kundalini:

- <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2444035/>
- <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1011343307783>
- <http://audiospiritual.com/pdf/Yoga/Kundalini%20-%20Evolution%20and%20Enlightenment.pdf>
- <http://knowledgefederation.project.ifi.uio.no/Misc/DR-slides.pdf>
- http://nutesla.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/Universal_Frequency_List_Ultimate_Edition1.pdf

Our Hands are channels of Divine Love. When we use them consciously, the Creative Power of the Cosmos is at our fingertips. ♥

Artist: Helena Nelson Reed

The Vortex centered at PC8, drawing power from outside and converting to heat, a known byproduct of Qi/prajna work.

Female Spin **Male Spin**

Male and Female - Yin and Yang
The direction in which a chakra rotates varies from chakra to chakra. Each chakra will spin or rotate in a different direction.

Tesla coil direction in the hand
 Those who have done Qi work, you can actually see a white circle on the outside of their hand, and in general, Qi work will manifest heat, as well as a mottled coloration on the hands, indicating strong microperfusion

The accepted generalized Truth for Male Transmitter/Receptor “data sharing” in all Qi gong and Prajnayana Note that females have the opposite spin.

Qi (specifically Essence Qi), and Neutrino Energy

After his initial videos, for those intrigued to know the full story, Professor Meyl provides some alternative explanations using the Electric Universe Model, where there is one Force (like Tao), namely the EM force. In it he describes such interesting and currently laughed at theories:

- The Sun AND the Earth's core are both near to Absolute Zero, rather than being millions of degrees
- Neutrinos coming from supernova can be focused by solar eclipses, and the central focus can lead to Earthquakes, which he used to successfully predict a 2006 Earthquake.
- Neutrino and anti-neutrino (just yin polarized neutrinos) radiation mostly passes through objects, BUT the Earth has both the ability to absorb them, and project them, and we can receive them.
- That proof of this lies in the facts that a) the Earth is growing despite what geologists might wish to ignore (by ~13 cm a year), b) the Sun's neutrino radiation is not reaching us due to magnetospherical shielding, hence our detections, even despite being a night or within mountains, are from Earth's Core, and c) the gravity in the core is 0, so the core cannot be extremely heavy and dense but instead light, and the densest materials are on the Earth's crust.
- That the neutrino radiation results in complex chemical changes in materials, such as water, and can even be resulting in the formation of oil - rather than dinosaurs and plant materials.
- Etc...

These theories seem mostly to fly in the face of conventional science. But so did Copernicus and Newton at one time. And Darwin. They must be thoroughly tested, not only in the laboratory but through theoretical math.

However, at this time I want to focus on the Earth is Growing factoid, which also caught the attention of geologists when he gave a talk at a conference on scalar magnetics.

There is a concept in Chinese Philosophy that says that Qi has 3 general categories of density: shen, qi, and jing- spirit, energy, and essence.

Putting aside the first, and relying on the ideas of quantum-relativity for the second, let us focus on the third. No one knows **what** Essence is. It has been written about in many languages and crops up again and again in all cultures. It is likely the idea that Aristotle was trying to purport with elements, as well as the fundamental idea of atoms. But we now know that atoms are not essence, they are a product of it.

This leaves the possibility to a number of sub-atomic particles, and of course spiritual ether. yet it cannot be purely spiritual ether because we also know that there are resultant products of essence from fertilization forward: bones, marrow, plasma/blood, CSF, semen, ovum, teeth, eyeballs, brain matter, even the myeloid around dendrites. All of these things belong to the category of Jing. Yet it isn't the molecules that make up Jing but their energetic constituent, because we also know in Ayurveda, TCM, and other life medicines, essence is stored, used, transported, transformed, and can be lost or built (cultivated), and even can result in spiritual ascension.

This seems to indicate a more complex wave-particle relationship than entire atoms.

What is interesting about the fact that the Earth grows, and the neutrino-power theory of the hydrogen cold-fusion core, is the fact that if the Earth is a living biosphere (as indeed has been proved since the 1960s), then this growth marks a similar behavior as described in the human with regards to Jing-Qi (Essence).

Could neutrinos be Jing? So far neutrino-detection labs have been located below mountains, in deserts, etc... there is no working method to find them in the body. Even the use of tesla coils and other detection systems is unlikely to prove viable for some time. Currently the EEG machines which are responsible for the spectacular

images of NatGeo's January 2014 issue can fill entire rooms. Until the detection machinery is small enough, and computers more able to handle the data downloads of entire brains (one brain takes about half the storage space of the entire world wide web's servers currently), this is unlikely to happen. After all, the brain is a quantum computer, and we have not even mastered optic or crystal computing, and true quantum computing is about as far off as cold fusion at the moment. But, it is my hypothesis that this, or some other particle that is responsible for the "Living Force" of Essence.

Astrology, Feng Shui, Geomancy, and Scalar Magnetics + Neutrinos

Another intriguing spin from these theories is their general hypothetical explanation of such strange macro-cosmic effects as in astrology and geomancy (including feng shui). We know from hospital and criminal data that the moon has a complex but slightly predictable effect on human health and behavior. For thousands of years people everywhere have noted these patterns. One explanation has always simply been "tides." But the ancients were not unaware of that phenomenon, and yet came up with such elaborate theories as "dragon's veins" or leylines. These ideas could have been early attempts at the sciences of astronomy and geology, terms that are markedly **just the same** as the others, but secularized to avoid religious or "superstitious" trappings. The times when these secularizing movements came about were roughly periods in Chinese and European history when the power of the Churches in government was desired to be curbed for political reasons. But as we know, scientific facts have never been alterable by politics, only hidden, marginalized, blunted, stunted, or covered-up. The facts remain. "It moves anyways," as Galileo said. So what are we to do with the geomantic and astrological data and research of thousands of generations? One idea is to discount them, place them in there with psychics and tarot a step above kool-aid drinking cults, and dismiss them from all policy.

Except, as it turns out this is a decidedly bad idea. Now that we have proof of magnetic tunneling from the sun, solar flares, solar winds, neutrino sprays from pulsars and nova, eclipse radiation, and other effects, and now that we know the Earth itself has radiation and strange changes, and now that we know the weather can indeed be altered by man in one way or another, how can we easily, without scientific analysis and thorough examination dismiss anything? It may well prove that the neutrino, higgs-boson, dark matter, antimatter, dark energy, or any number of as yet not understood particle is responsible for a large number of important changes.

At one time there was a man named Semmelweis, who was a proponent of the Germ Theory. At that time doctors did not wash their hands, ever, except to wash off blood. This was before Pasteur. He proved however that washing hands would save women in post delivery infections, reducing deaths from 18% to 2.2%. He was however, ostracized and declared insane. There is a portion of the brain which engages in Confirmation Bias, and can not only cause people to hate change or anything that threatens their worldview, but even cause them to not see material/ideas **at all**, ignoring anything foreign until life forces them to change.

The Earth is right now, degrading in magnetic power, and may in very short time force humans to deal with a larger number of unknown particles. As the Earth's gravity increases, of course, it too may change many "facts" we hold dear, such as in the old days people thinking the Earth was flat. Even Einstein could not have known that most of the stars he saw were in fact galaxies with billions of stars each. At his time, the Milky Way was considered the only galaxy or one of only a few. And a mere fifty years prior to that, most astronomers thought that stars sat merely just outside the solar system. In that time we have gone from the Enlightenment - when we thought we were about to know everything and no longer needed God (now that we had Darwin and

Maxwell), to thinking we know less than 4% of what is out there. That number shrinks every year. This is of course the result of a fractal universe being observed through derivation.

My point is that perhaps with these studies, it may be time to dust off the ancient books, or even more commonly used ones such as the Farmer's Almanac, and do some new scientific analysis testing new models that are more encompassing, rather than anthropologically exclusionary. For example, for 60 years the Big Bang was the accepted model. Until only recently they realized it was merely a rewritten Genesis - literally - and actually it wasn't a Bang but an Expansion.

Here are three videos which have thrown the scientific community into confusion, and show strong issues in the current paradigms:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wRsGPq77X0Q>

<http://youtu.be/Y0c5nIvJH7w>

<http://youtu.be/JKHUaNAxsTg>

In Conclusion

The acquisition of a Meyl experimental Tesla coil kit may enable the Qi/prajna/reiki healer or homeopathic, naturopathic, and/or herbal practitioner to put a quantifiable measurement behind their work. Already thermography has made great strides, especially in combination with Corellian photography to show the presence of etheric fields (auras) and demonstrate the possibility of supernatural seeming powers (which are inherent to the developed human). However, they are not enough, because the medical and scientific community are not ready from an ethical, moral, cultural, and evolutionary standpoint (and perhaps impeded by ulterior motives to not become ready) to accept Qi without **data**.

Although CAM research is advanced to the point of moving RCT/double blind placebos (which are generally irrelevant to such healing modalities) from the list of prime research methods to secondary, the fact remains that clinical trials are not sufficient to endorse and attract significant funding for these modalities. The discovery or correlative evidence strongly indicating the presence of measurable effects (if large enough machines could be constructed), could enhance or alter the direction of funding.

To help the scientific and medical community change from a purely chemical view of the body to an obviously more viable, intriguing, accurate, and time-tested bio-energetic-electromagnetic quantum view where the sharing of modulated data is not purely atoms moving about, but information processed in a hyper-dimensional holographic quantum machine, **data** must be acquired.

This would demonstrate a body where healing from cancers and other chronic degenerative disorders is no longer the exception but the inevitability of energy flow enhancement; and such terms as cancer, AIDS, or heart attack are detached from the stigma of "death sentence". This would create a world of less fear, and more self-empowerment and compassionate medicine! Thank you.